

METHODS OF TEACHING MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY AT EFL CLASSES

Kuziev Sarvarbek Ilmiddinovich

Fergana State University

Teacher of the English Department of the Faculty of Foreign Languages

Usmonova Xurinisa Sharapovna

Namangan state university

Doctor of philological sciences, professor

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Annotation: This paper examines the combination of two academic approaches including components of a present practice produce strategy as well as task based learning in arrange to assist understudies learn and effortlessly keep in mind the medical terminology . The viability of instructional method regularly depends on the subject to be instructed , on learners needs and on adjusting to the on the ground conditions within the classroom.

In the primary portion , we are going compare two instructing models the presentation practice production and the task based learning considering both viable to organizing and arranging lessons.

In the second segment of the paper, we'll display a few learning speculations such as, platform, historical underpinnings and memory helpers, a few visual devices which help learners understanding and memory since it fits with the brains strategy of preparing information.

The final portion will center on the vocabulary EFL understudies got to learn in case they confront a genuine life medical circumstance.

Key words: medical terminology, teaching methods, PPT, TBL

Introduction

Learning is subordinate on the academic approaches instructors utilize within the classroom. A assortment of academic approaches are common, but a few techniques are more viable than others. Understudies seeking after careers in medical areas, medical attendants, specialists and other medical experts must be capable in medical terminology, methods and ideas in arrange to work in a native English talking nation, to development in their display position or to unravel issues in their professions.

From my encounter educating English for restorative purposes I consider that, when instructing lexicon, for case, we cannot fair deliver a list of words or sentences learner should secure both the frame and the assortment of implications of a given lexical thing. That's why we require all kind of visual apparatuses and diversions and other educating strategies to form less demanding the memorization.

Ninety percent of medical lexicon come from Greek and Latin words and can be effectively isolated in prefixes, additions and roots for being memorized. For case amygdectomy is shaped of amygdale, the organ and ectomy meaning extraction. But words like cholera, skin inflammation, typhus come from antiquated medical hypothesis and need to be learned exclusively like figures of speech of the dialect.

But how to keep in mind a word like pneumonoultramicroscopicsilicovolcanoconiosis having 45 letters given as an illustration by Lesley A. Dean Jones in the Classical Journal 1998 292 meaning an irregular condition of the lungs caused by amazingly fine particles of silicon clean transmitted from a volcano .

2. PPP approach versus TBL approach

The display area centers on a comparison between two instructing models the popular PPP (Presentation, Practice and Production) and the TBL Task Based Learning learner centred approaches.

The PPP approach (presentation, practice, production) points to instruct a particular dialect frame and makes a difference under studies to practice the new words. Under studies rehash and apply the dialect, at that point hone within the shape of talked and composed works out and at long last utilized the shapes in less controlled talking or writing exercises. The PPP approach, but amid the ultimate generation organize, is teacher based.

An alternative to the PPP approach is the TBL task based learning in which the production stage comes to begin with, and after that learners think and analyze, whereas educator mediates as it were when required.

Task-based learning has three stages:

- The pre-task stage (teacher introduces and defines the topic and the learners engage in activities that either help them to recall words and phrases or to learn new words and phrases that are essential to the task).
- The "task cycle" (learners perform the task in pairs or small groups and then prepare a report for the whole class).
- The final stage is the language focus stage, during which specific language features from the task are highlighted and worked on. Feedback on the learners' performance could be also done.

Whereas the aim of the PPP model is to lead from accuracy to fluency, the aim of TBL is to integrate all four skills and to move from fluency to accuracy plus fluency.

2.1 How can I use PPP approach in the classroom?

Most of the PPP lessons follow the following structure:

- LEAD-IN: can be verbal (using stories, dialogues, songs) or it can be material (pictures, grammar point, audiovisual, illustrations etc). For example if we want to teach human body we can show our learners pictures with parts of the body.
- ELICITATION: the most common way of eliciting is to ask questions for getting as much information on the vocabulary point: how do we call this part of the body? Which part of the body we use to smell?
- PRESENTATION: can be deductive or inductive. The focus is on the form at this stage. The teacher gives example with word formation and let students discover the rule.
- CONTROLLED PRACTICE: in this stage, the focus is on accuracy, not on use or application. There should be one correct answer and teacher already knows the answer.
- FREE PRACTICE (PRODUCE): the activities during this stage are related to students' own life and there are lots of correct answers.
- HOMEWORK: teacher gives homework for students to practice what they learned. Clear instructions with details should be given.

2.1 How can I use TBL in the classroom?

Most of the task-based lessons have this structure:

- Lead-in
- Brainstorming ideas in group
- Feedback from the group

- Introducing the task
- Establishing the task
- Practice
- Feedback
- Introducing the writing task
- Setting up the task
- Task-homework

In TBL, the central focus of the lesson is the task itself. The advantage of TBL over more traditional methods is that it focuses on students' needs by putting them into authentic communicative situations, expose learners to a wide variety of language and not just grammar and it is good for mixed ability classes; a task can be completed successfully by a weaker or a stronger student.

3. So how can students learn medical vocabulary?

It is crucial to take into account your students' learning styles when teaching English language. We are giving a brief description of each style.

Auditory learners are able to recall what they hear and prefer oral instructions. They learn by listening and speaking, they are phonetic readers. They learn by interviewing, debating, giving oral reports etc.

Visual learners are able to recall what they see and prefer written instructions. They will learn by observing and enjoy working with computer graphics, maps, graphic organizers, pictures etc. Tactile learners learn best by touching and benefit from reading. They will learn by drawing, playing board games, making models etc.

- Learn vocabulary by theme. It is easier to learn words by related themes than isolated or random.

- Use games in class. Game-based learning is a teaching method that allows learners to study English by games being perceived like a form of entertainment.

These are some of the most efficient techniques for teaching or learning vocabulary. The objective for teaching medical terminology is also to teach students how to decipher medical terms.

In a word we have a prefix, a root and a suffix. In the following table we present a categorization of prefixes used in medical words.

Table 1- Categorization of some medical prefixes

Prefixes size and amount	Prefixes numerical	Prefixes-Speed	Prefixes-Location	Prefixes movements	Prefixes colours	General prefixes
macro-large micro-small hyper-high hypo-low normo-normal omni-all	mono-single di-double tri-triple quad-four poly-many oligo-few	Tachy- fast Brady/brachy slow	Epi/peri/circum Around Endo/intra-inside Exo/extra-outside Inter-between Trans-across Dia/per-complete	Ab-away Abduction Ad-toward Dis-to separate	Chromo colour Leuko white Erythro-red Cyano-blue Chloro green	Homeo-body Cephalo-head Cerv-neck Thoraco-chest Abdomino abdominal Pelvo-pelvic Periton Periton peritoneum

a/an- absent megalo large			Medi-middle Para-nearby Juxta-next to		Melan- black Flav- yellow	Derm-skin Neuro-nerve Hemo-blood Arterio/angio arteries Veno-venous Vasculo- vascular Myo/sarco muscle Skelet- skeleton Osteo-bone Cyto-cell
Prefixes for neck and thoracic organs				Prefixes for abdominal organs		
Thyro-thyroid Tracheo-trachea Esophago- esophagus Thymo- thymus Masto-mammary glands Pulmo/pneumo-lung Cardio- heart				Gastro-stomach Hepato-liver Cholecysto – gallbladder Spleno-spleen Pancreato-pancreas Adreno-adrenal glands Nephro-kidney Entero-intestines Colo-colon		

This categorization can be organized in a mind-map or schemata or used in a bingo game. Nurses and doctors need to be very familiar with illnesses, their symptoms, and the accompanying treatments. We thought about some topics students would need to know if they faced a real life medical situation. These topics are:

- Medical staff
- Medical conditions
- Types of pain and treatments
- Ailments and injuries
- Signs and symptoms
- Human body
- Giving direction in a hospital
- Making appointments

Conclusion

In this paper we underlined two teaching approaches and sketched some techniques for medical vocabulary acquisition. Both PPT and TBL focus on the achievement of the objectives, and then on the language that is needed to achieve these objectives. A combination of TBL, PPP and the other teaching techniques that we presented like mind-mapping, mnemonics, games etc. give plenty of opportunities for communication in authentic contexts and give learners the freedom to reflect on what they learned or need to learn. Vocabulary learning is a memory, task but it involves creative use too.

References:

1. Lesley A. Dean-Jones, *The Classical Journal*, Vol. 93, No. 3 (Feb. - Mar., 1998), pp. 290-296
2. Lev Vygotsky Archive. (No date). Retrieved November 15, 2002, from <http://www.marxists.org/archive/vygotsky/>
3. Raymond, E. (2000). Cognitive Characteristics. *Learners with Mild Disabilities* (pp. 169-201). Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon, A Pearson Education Company.
4. Ilmaddinovich, K. S. (2021). The methodologies of learning english vocabulary among foreign language learners. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 501-505.
5. Ilmaddinovich, K. S. (2020). Methods Of Teaching English To Young Learners. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(11), 65-69.
6. Ilmaddinovich, K. S. (2022). Integrating 21st Century Skills into Teaching Medical Terminology. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 9, 114-117.
7. Ilmaddinovich, K. S. (2020). Online evaluating the language learners on the platforms of the social networking services and delivery people. *International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences (IJRESS)*, 10(11).
8. Numonjohnovna, E. N., Ugli, B. B. B., & Ilmaddinovich, K. S. (2019). Problems in developing speaking skills of students of technical higher educational institutions. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (12-1 (145)), 95-96.
9. Кузиев, С. И. (2020). Общение между врачами и медицинскими работниками: роль и ранг медицинской терминологии в хирургии, здравоохранении и истории медицины. *Вестник науки и образования*, (13-3 (91)), 29-31.
10. Kuziev, S. (2022). AT ENGLISH CLASSES USING APPROACHES AND METHODS OF ON TEACHING SPECIAL TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 2(12), 265-269.
11. Кузиев, С. И. (2020). COMMUNICATION AMONG PHYSICIANS AND HEALTHCARE ASSOCIATES: THE ROLE AND RANK OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN SURGERY, PUBLIC HEALTH AND THE HISTORY OF MEDICINE. *Вестник науки и образования*, (13-3), 29-31.
12. Ilmaddinovich, Q. S. (2023). NOLIGVISTIK FAKULTETLARDA KASBGA YO'NALTIRILGAN CHET TILINI O'QITISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 3(30), 83-93.
13. Kuziyev, S. (2023, May). SIGNIFICANCE OF TERMS IN PROFESSIONAL FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. In *International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science* (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 85-89).
14. Quziyev, S. (2023). CHET TILINI O'QITISHNING LINGVODIDAKTIK ASOSLARI. *Наука и инновация*, 1(7), 120-124.
15. Kuziyev, S. (2023, May). DISTINCTIVE ADVANTAGES OF LEARNING AND TEACHING SPECIFIC DICTIONARIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES OF NON-PHILOLOGY HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. In *International Conference on Business Management and Humanities* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 127-129).
16. Kuziyev, S. (2023, May). TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO MEDICAL STUDENTS. In *International Conference On Higher Education Teaching* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 117-119).
17. Quziyev, S. (2023). MAXSUS ATAMALARNI O'QITISHNING NAZARIY METODIK

ASOSLARI. *Молодые ученые*, 1(3), 92-95.

18. Imiddinovich, Q. S. (2023). CHET TILLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY METODLARINI TAKKOMILLASHTIRISH ASSOSLARI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 2(18), 14-19.

19. Quziyev, S. (2022). Sarvar TIBBIYOT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA CHET TILINI O'QITISH JARAYONIDA TIBBIYOT ATAMALARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI: TIBBIYOT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA CHET TILINI O'QITISH JARAYONIDA TIBBIYOT ATAMALARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(4).

20. Kuziev, S. I. (2022). MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AT MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(11), 242-245.

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